

ARRIVE 2.0 Author Checklist (Table Format) – *Platyrrhinus helleri*

Item	Recommendation	Section / Line Number or Reason for Not Reporting
1	Study design	This study reports the generation of a reference genome assembly from a single male individual of <i>Platyrrhinus helleri</i> . No experimental or control groups were used, as this is a descriptive genome sequencing study. The experimental unit was one individual animal.
2	Sample size	a. One experimental unit (n = 1 individual animal) was used. b. No sample size calculation was performed, as the objective was to generate a reference genome from a single high-quality specimen, consistent with Vertebrate Genome Project and Bat1K standards.
3	Inclusion and exclusion criteria	a. No formal inclusion or exclusion criteria were applied beyond species identification and specimen suitability for high-molecular-weight DNA extraction. b. No animals or data were excluded from the analysis. c. n = 1 for all analyses.
4	Randomisation	Randomisation was not applicable, as no experimental groups or comparative interventions were used.
5	Blinding	Blinding was not applicable, as this study involved no treatment allocation or outcome comparison.
6	Outcome measures	a. Outcome measures included genome assembly size, contiguity metrics (contig and scaffold N50), BUSCO completeness scores, and chromosomal assignment. b. This was not a hypothesis-testing study; therefore, no primary outcome measure was defined for sample size determination.
7	Statistical methods	a. No inferential statistical analyses were performed. Assembly quality metrics were generated using established bioinformatic tools (e.g. BUSCO, Merqury, BlobToolKit). b. Statistical assumptions were not applicable.
8	Experimental animals	Species: <i>Platyrrhinus helleri</i> ; Sex: Male; Developmental stage: Adult; Weight: Not recorded; Provenance: Wild-caught individual collected at Lamanai Archaeological Reserve, Orange Walk District, Belize; Health status: No abnormalities observed; Genetic modification: None; Previous procedures: None reported.
9	Experimental procedures	Procedures are described in sufficient detail to allow replication, including: • Capture using a ground-level mist net • Species identification based on morphology and morphometrics • Humane euthanasia by isoflurane

		inhalation • Tissue collection and preservation • DNA extraction • PacBio HiFi and Hi-C sequencing • Genome assembly and curation pipeline. Rationale for procedures is provided in the context of generating a high-quality chromosome-level genome assembly.
10	Results	Genome sequence report; Tables 1–3; Figures 3–6. Assembly metrics, descriptive statistics, and completeness scores are reported. Effect sizes and confidence intervals are not applicable.

The Recommended Set

Item	Recommendation	Section / Line Number or Reason for Not Reporting
11	Abstract	The abstract summarises the study objective, species used, sequencing approach, and key assembly outcomes.
12	Background	Sufficient background is provided on <i>Platyrrhinus helleri</i> , its taxonomy, ecology, morphology, and the importance of generating a reference genome within the Bat1K initiative.
13	Objectives	Section: Introduction. The objective was to generate and publicly release a high-quality chromosome-level reference genome assembly for <i>Platyrrhinus helleri</i> .
14	Ethical statement	Section: Ethics. Ethical approval was obtained from: • American Museum of Natural History Institutional Animal Care and Use Committee (AMNH IACUC-20210614) • Belize Forest Department Permit FD/WL/1/21(16) • Belize Institute of Archaeology Permit IA/S/5/6/21(01) • Export permit FD/WL/7/22(07).
15	Housing and husbandry	Section: Not applicable. The animal was wild-caught and was not housed in captivity.
16	Animal care and monitoring	Section: Methods; Ethics. Steps taken to minimise pain and distress included minimal handling after capture, temporary holding in a clean cloth bag following best practices, and humane euthanasia by isoflurane inhalation. No adverse events occurred. Humane endpoints consisted of euthanasia immediately following species identification and tissue collection.
17	Interpretation / scientific implications	Section: Genome sequence report. Results are interpreted in the context of genome quality, chromosomal completeness, and their contribution to the Bat1K initiative and comparative bat genomics. Limitations associated with sequencing a single representative individual are inherent to the study design.

18	Generalisability / translation	Section: Genome sequence report. The genome assembly provides a reference resource for comparative genomics, evolutionary biology, and conservation studies of phyllostomid bats. No direct translational or human biological relevance is claimed.
19	Protocol registration	Section: Not applicable. No pre-registered experimental protocol was required for this descriptive genome sequencing study.
20	Data access	Section: Data availability. The genome assembly is publicly available through the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) under the reported accession number, with associated BioProject information provided in the manuscript.
21	Declaration of interests	Section: Competing Interests; Grant Information. All authors declare no competing interests. Funding sources are reported, and the funders had no role in study design, data collection, analysis, decision to publish, or manuscript preparation.